

Effect of Substituents on Bond Length. Part I

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A preliminary survey of variations in bond length of a large number of compounds has been made. The presence of functional groups, such as OH, Me, COOH, Ph, etc., in a molecule causes the bond length to change in many cases. There is, however, no appreciable change in the derivatives of acetylene. Reasons are discussed and a mechanism is suggested to fit in such changes.

Coulson¹ has suggested that the factors influencing the bond length are bond order, hybridisation, and formal charge distribution and he tried to correlate bond lengths in organic molecules from these factors. He has at the same time pointed out that these alone could not cover cases where variations occur in bond length. According to Brown², hybridisation effects are adequate for discussing bond length. He has indicated that hybridisation effects lead to a satisfactory assignment of atomic radii of C—C bonds. Recently Bernstein³ has suggested a scheme for calculating bond lengths in hydrocarbons. For the relatively simple compounds, hybridisation effect appears, however, to be adequate to account for bond lengths, but it may not be so in other cases. For a systematic study, ethane may be considered first. The variation in its C—C bond length, caused by substitution of the hydrogen atoms by other groups, is interesting.

Substitution of a group, such as Me, Ph, COOH, NO₂, Cl, Br, etc., in a molecule causes electron displacements (by inductive or mesomeric mechanism) with the result that polarisation occurs. In other words, the charge cloud of the molecular orbital is appreciably affected. When this effect is large, the bond length may change.

TABLE I

Hexamethylethane	*1.58 ± 0.03 Å	Succinic acid	*1.50 Å
(±)-Tartaric acid hydrate	*1.53	Ethylene glycol	1.52 ± 0.02
Tartrate ion	*1.53	Dibenzyl	**1.51
(+)-Tartaric acid	*1.47	<i>pp'</i> -Dimethyldibenzyl	*1.53

**Crystalline, accuracy ± 0.02 Å.

*Crystalline, accuracy ± 0.05 Å.

The Ph, OH, and COOH groups have (-I) effect. The presence of any of these appears to cause a shortening of the bond length. Thus the central C—C bond in succinic acid, ethylene glycol, and dibenzyl is shorter than that in ethane. On the other hand, the Me

N.B. Except where mentioned, all bond lengths are from Sutton *et al.*, "Inter-atomic Distances in Molecules and Ions", Chemical Society, London, Special Publication No. 11.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 311.

2. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1950, 55, 604.

3. *Ibid.*, 1961, 57, 1640.

group has (+I) effect and it appears to increase the bond length as in hexamethylethane. In *pp'*-dimethyldibenzyl, the bond has, however, a normal length; probably the effect of the Ph group and that of *p*-Me group balance each other. The case of the tartrate ion is similar; carboxylate ion (+I effect) and hydroxyl ion balance each other. In tartaric acid, both groups have the same effect and as such there is a greater shortening of the bond length. It further appears that both carbon atoms of ethane have to be symmetrically substituted to affect bond length.

It is suggested that substituents with (-I) effect would tend to stretch the molecular orbital of the central bond, i.e., the electron-charge cloud of the orbital would tend to spread out. This effect appears to be counterbalanced by the carbon atoms coming closer together. The presence of (+I) substituents would lead to an opposite kind of effect.

A halogen atom is known to exert a strong (-I) effect. It appears that substitution of halogen atoms in ethane does not, however, affect the central C-C bond length. Some values of bond length for halogen-substituted ethane do not appear to be quite reliable.

According to Bent^{3a}, bond lengths, bond angles, etc. are affected by electronegative substituents. Mulliken⁴ has discussed effective hybridisation, using Coulson's equation⁵ for the "hybridisation ratio, λ , of an orbital $s + \lambda p\sigma$. This fails to indicate the effect on bond radii with change in valence angle. It is not necessary that change in valence angle should affect the bond length too. Thus in cyclopropane (1.53 Å), cyclobutane (1.56 Å), cyclopentane (1.54 Å), and cyclohexane (1.54 Å), the bonds appear to have the normal length.

In certain cases, the variation in bond length may be due to steric effect or some other cause. More precise measurements would throw much light on the nature and extent of the effect. A few examples are acenaphthene⁶ (1.64 Å), spiro-pentane (1.48 Å), di-*m*-xylylene (1.60 Å), butane (1.51 ± 0.05 Å).

Mulliken⁴ has pointed out that the concept of definite bond radii is only an approximation and has cited the examples of the covalent radii of hydrogen in several compounds. On this basis alone, he has supported the postulate of Dewar⁷ that the bond radii of carbon in "trigonal" and "digonal" bond orbitals are considerably smaller in C-C than in C-H. The covalent radius of hydrogen, however, appears to decrease with the increase in the electronegativity of the combining atoms. As carbon in the "trigonal" and "digonal" states is more electronegative, it is likely that the covalent radius of the hydrogen in ethylene, acetylene, etc. will be smaller. Consequently, the bond radii of carbon may be a little longer. As such, this would not be a sure guide in estimating the central C-C bond in 1,3-butadiene or diacetylene.

The C-C, C-H, and C-halogen distances for a large number of compounds have been reviewed by Brown². The values recorded by him for different types of bonds are shown below for comparison.

3a. *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 275.

4. *Tetrahedron*, 1959, 6, 68.

5. V. Henry Memorial Volume, p. 15. Desoer Liege, 1948.

6. Kitaigorodski, *Chem. Abst.*, 1950, 44, 897.

7. *Tetrahedron*, 1950, 5, 166.

TABLE II

Bond radii.		Bond length (calc.).	
$sp^3 - sp^3$	0.772 Å	$sp^3 - sp^2$	1.505 Å
$sp^2 - sp^2$	0.733	$sp^3 - sp$	1.459
$sp - sp$	0.687	$sp^2 - sp$	1.420

A detailed list of C—C bond lengths in different states of hybridisation has also been compiled by Bent^{3a}. All these bond lengths have been calculated on the assumption that hyperconjugation or π -electron resonance has no effect on C—C distances. This view has been strongly advocated by Dewar⁷. From a qualitative study of bond lengths, Sutton⁸ could not come to any definite conclusion on this question. On the other hand, Mulliken⁴ from calculations has found that sufficient correction is necessary for π -electron resonance and hyperconjugation. According to him, the central bond in 1,3-butadiene (sp^2 - sp^2 bond) should be 1.51 Å. [This is shortened to 1.46 Å (observed value) due to π -electron resonance]. For molecules, where hyperconjugation is expected, he has estimated the "natural length" of a sp^3 - sp^2 bond to be 1.51 Å. It is thus obvious that sp^3 - sp^2 and sp^2 - sp^2 bonds are expected to have the same "natural lengths" and hence hybridisation effect does not appear to be of much importance. This does not appear to be a happy conclusion.

In any case, C—C distance in a sp^3 - sp^2 bond is expected to be appreciably shorter than that in sp^3 - sp^3 on consideration of hybridisation effect alone. The observed bond lengths in some compounds are recorded below.

TABLE III

<i>cis</i> -2-Butene	*1.54 ± 0.30 Å	*Hexamethylbenzene	1.54 ± 0.01 Å
<i>trans</i> -2-Butene	*1.56 ± 0.04	*Mesitylene	1.54 ± 0.01
<i>cis</i> -2-Butene oxide	*1.54 ± 0.03	Octamethylnaphthalene	1.54 ^a 1.55 ^a
<i>trans</i> -2-Butene oxide	*1.54 ± 0.03	Tetraphenylmethane	1.47 (error uncertain)

*One or more parameters assumed.

In almost all cases the sp^3 - sp^2 distances evidently are 1.54 Å. Thus hyperconjugation is not having any appreciable effect on the C—C distances. In fact, explanation is needed for the lengthening of the sp^3 - sp^2 bond.

It is suggested that one of the main factors responsible for the increase in length of the sp^3 - sp^2 bond is the greater electron density on the sp^2 -hybridised C atoms due to presence of mobile π -electrons in the double bond or as in the benzene or naphthalene ring. Thus the C—Me (sp^2 - sp^3) bond in the *cis*- and *trans*-butenes is much longer. Similar is the case of mesitylene, hexamethylbenzene, octamethylnaphthalene, etc. Steric interactions leading to the van der Waals overlap of the hydrogen atoms of the methyl group could not be altogether ruled out in the case of such compounds as hexamethylbenzene and octamethylnaphthalene, but these do not appear to play an appreciable part so far as the C—Me bond is concerned.

The sp^2 - sp^2 single bond (central bond), as in biphenyl (1.54 ± 0.03 Å, 1.48 Å), would be expected to be greater on account of the presence of mobile π -electron in the benzene

rings; in other words, the electron density on the two carbon atoms forming the central bond is sufficiently great to cause elongation of the bond. Electron-attracting or electron-repelling groups in *o*- or *p*-position in the benzene rings of biphenyl may also affect the length of the central bond (Table IV).

TABLE IV

3,3'-Dibromobiphenyl	1.49 Å	2,2'-Dichlorobenzidine	1.53 Å
4,4'-Dinitrobiphenyl	1.42	3,3'-Dichlorobenzidine	1.50
	(error uncertain)	<i>m</i> -Toluidine hydrochloride	1.52
		<i>m</i> -Tolidine	1.55

It has been pointed out by Walsh⁹ that the ionisation potential of ethylene decreases when Me group is substituted. This is partly due to the electron-releasing properties of Me, causing increase of electron repulsion. Thus the C—C double bond should become longer and this is actually found in *cis*-(1.38 Å) and *trans*-butene (1.40 Å). Similarly the introduction of halogens should shorten the C—C double bond and this is generally found to be true in the case of halogen-substituted ethylenes. But more precise measurements appear necessary for definite conclusions.

The bond lengths of acetylene and its derivatives indicate that there is practically no change in the bond length in any case. This is perhaps due to the fact that the electrons in bigger acetylene (π -ionisation potential 11.41 ± 0.01 v) are more tightly bound than those of ethylene (π -ionisation potential 10.50 ± 0.03 v). It has also been pointed out by Walsh⁹ that the tighter binding of the π -electron in acetylene means that these will conjugate less completely, *i.e.*, remain more localised in their original C—C bond than do the π -electrons of ethylene. It is therefore quite apparent that the bond lengths in acetylene and its derivatives would not change appreciably either by conjugation or from the presence of any type of group. This view falls in line with that of Dewar⁷.

CONCLUSION

Substitution of groups having ($-I$) effects in ethane leads to an increase of the C—C distance, but groups with ($+I$) effect shorten the bond length. This effect appears to a smaller extent in ethylene derivatives, but is absent in acetylene derivatives. Mulliken's observations on the natural length of some bonds do not appear convincing.